

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Karimova Mokhira Jumakulovna

Teacher Department of languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7217610>

Abstract. *This article focuses on productive types of speech activity, which is especially important for mastering a foreign language. The Article specifies how effective work with special texts in a foreign language helps to formulate the necessary language and communication skills for students in a non-native language and promotes the development of their common scientific knowledge and skills.*

Key words: *language acquisition, inter-language, language experience, language awareness, fossilization, remedy, redundant language features, proficiency levels, cognitive process, «bottom-up» processing data-driven, «top-down» conceptual-driven processing, input, output, target language, approximation, process-oriented approach, product-oriented approach, communicative data, principles, methods, surface and deeper levels, system of exercises.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В данной статье основное внимание уделяется продуктивным видам речевой деятельности, что особенно важно для овладения иностранным языком. В статье указывается, как эффективная работа со специальными текстами на иностранном языке помогает формировать у учащихся необходимые языковые и коммуникативные навыки на неродном языке и способствует развитию у них общенаучных знаний и умений.*

Ключевые слова: *овладение языком, интерязык, языковой опыт, языковая осведомленность, фоссилзация, средство, избыточные языковые особенности, уровни владения языком, когнитивный процесс, обработка данных «снизу вверх», управляемая данными обработка «сверху вниз», концептуальная обработка, вход, выход, целевой язык, аппроксимация, процессно-ориентированный подход, продуктивно-ориентированный подход, коммуникативные данные, принципы, методы, поверхностный и глубинный уровни, система упражнений.*

INTRODUCTION

Language acquisition and language experience's necessary, first, to understand the differences between acquiring a native and foreign languages. The native language is a language the child acquires since being born. The foreign language is one of the variants of the non-native languages. Another variant of a non-native language is the second language, his admitted the native language as a functional language because it is used for everyday communication. The second language usually refers to any language that is not the first (native) one learns. While contrasting the native, the second and foreign languages, the terms «first language» (L1), «second language» (L2 or SL), and «foreign language» (FL) are used. The major difference between FL and SL learning is that a FL is learned in the artificial language environment, outside of the social environment, in the teaching conditions. Besides, the FL is not the means of everyday communication. But at the same time, we cannot line out the distinction between them, because the FL can become for learners as a SL or vice versa. For instance, in the English speaking countries migrants learn English as a SL, for Uzbekistan the EL is the foreign language.

Between LI, L2 or FL acquisition we can point out the following common theoretical features:

1) the foundation for L2/ FL is built largely from a transfer of the rules of LI; 2) only L2/ FL is constructed from prior conceptual knowledge within the learner. The learners of L2/FL use similar strategies to those learning their first language. Although L2/FL learners go through essentially the same process as LI learners, they do it much faster because they are usually more advanced cognitively. The EL as a subject at school, lyceum and college is studied by students on the basis of the language and social-cultural experience. By the language experience we understand a language practice of students in operating with language units during communication.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The language experience contents: educational informativeness, language store (lexical, pronunciation, grammar, etc.), and ability of transmission and getting the information in correspondence to the syllabus requirements. Language experience in the LI is replaced into the learning FL, which has positive and negative character. In FL methodology positive side is called transposition (fossilization) and negative one is interference. Teaching/learning FL presupposes acquiring «inter-language» because the language experience combines two languages that follow to forming the mixed code. The term «inter-language» refers to the development stages involved in moving from LI to L2/FL; various kinds of errors and strategies have been identified with stages along the way. For example, learners at some levels in early stage of their development have difficulty with sentence inversion when asking a question (e.g. They do incorrect word order of questions -You are in the garden?), and with the negative formation (They do incorrect form of negative sentence - You no in the garden). Learners tend to vary their inter-language. In the methodology the terms of FLT and FLL are also distinguished. The FLT is a specially organized process, during which as a result of interaction of a teacher with students, the reproduction and acquiring a certain experience are accomplished in correspondence with the given goal. The FLL is the conscious and goal-oriented activity directed at acquiring structural characteristics of the language (pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar). The ELL is a natural, cognitive process with learners ultimately responsible for their own learning. Language acquisition (LI, L2, FL) poses the unconscious intuitive uncontrolled activity. It is effective to learn or acquire the language in a real language environment. Being, outside of environment of the native speakers is the main reason of the appearance of the language barrier and fossilization. Thus, one of the objectives of a teacher is maximal approximation of teaching situation to the real language environment involving the native speakers. As J.L.Clark stressed, « Acquisition is not a linear cumulative process but a gradual developmental one, in which many knowledge elements are all growing at once, at different rates, and at different levels of perfection. Most knowledge is not immediately accommodated on first presentation. A gestation period, in which further exposure to the same knowledge elements occurs in different contexts, is normally necessary before data can be fully incorporated into the implicit knowledge store». Having already acquired an LI non-native students are aware of the intentionality of language use and of the functions that language serves. They are thus primed to seek out prepositional meaning and illocutionary value with all the faculties and experience that they can bring to bear on the matter. That's why, when interpreting real talk or text, FL beginners devote most of their attention to

processing the essential semantic units. The more or less redundant language features can simply not be attended to. In the information-processing theory «bottom-up» data-driven processing and «top-down» conceptually-driven processing are defined (described in detail by J.L. Clark). «Bottom-up» data-driven processing permits us to attend to perceptions, organize them, and then extract meaning from them. «Top-down» conceptually-driven processing enables us to obtain a rapid prediction of what is likely to occur on the basis of previous experience, and to match this against the incoming sensory data. We (I don't have to process all the bottom-up information available to us through our senses, since we use the top-down contextual clues and predictions based on past experiences and general knowledge to avoid having to process the whole input. New information is triggered as a result of expectations produced by top-down processing. I have continually merging with the data derived from bottom-up processes where tasks encountered present novel problems with little relationship to existing schemata and with few contextual clues, the effective bottom-up processing becomes very important where tasks present familiar problems, top-down processing may provide rapid solution. Two different kinds of information-processing are distinguished. Controlled-processing is involved when conscious attention is required to perform a task; this places demands on short-form memory. Automatic-processing is involved when the learner carries out a task without awareness or attention, making greater use of information in long-term memory. Learning involves the performance of behavior by automatic-processing. The information-processing model explains as to why learner's language use sometimes shifts from fluent (automatic-processing) to less fluent (controlled-processing) and why learners in the initial stages of language learning need to put so much effort into understanding and producing language'.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Learners are not simple input-output mechanisms, not all acquired knowledge and information (input) can be reproduced and produced in a novel context (output) by them. Effective output depends on methods, techniques and exercises which we use in classrooms. Learner can acquire language from communication, gradually the learners' communicative resource improves and expands, and approximates to the native speakers. Very few learners can achieve a communicative resource equal to that of a native speaker, but given appropriate data and tasks, learners can learn to communicate successfully in FL. While linguistic competence is necessary to all communication, much can be done with minimal grammar and adequate vocabulary. In methodology the term «language awareness» as «development in learners of an enhanced consciousness of and sensitivity to the forms and functions of language» is used. Other definitions that reflect the core of language awareness is consciousness-raising; form-focus instruction, form interpretation tasks. Language awareness includes itself awareness about grammar, lexical, phonological, and discourse features, i.e. language data. The goal of language awareness is to develop in the learners' awareness of and sensitivity to form, meaning and function of the language English. Learners have to explore structured input and develop an awareness of particular linguistic features by performing certain operations. It is not the same thing as practice, because it involves input processing, noticing certain patterns or relationships, discovering rules, and noticing the difference between native and learned languages and current inter-language. Language awareness is data-driven. Learners are not told the rule, but are given a set of data from

which they infer the rule or generalization in their own way for using in communication. It is process-oriented approach, which includes steps of discovery, investigation, and understanding, which contrasts markedly with the traditional product-oriented approach in which learners are told the rules and have to drill and memorize them. Language awareness builds inter-language which has to grow and develop; otherwise, fossilization sets-learners may exhibit of the all-too-familiar symptoms of language gaps. Many learners seem to experience this gap and need remedial work in order to eradicate fossilized errors. Learners need communicative data, because these provide the essential input upon which their mental language learning process can operate. It is important to provide them with appropriate level of contextual support to assist them, and to encourage them to transfer to the language learning situation the same strategies that they use to predict and guess meaning through context and word-building elements. Communicative data in English classroom contents: teacher's talk; other classroom talk; recordings of talk (audio and video); pedagogically-inspired written information; other classroom information; realia and written texts from outside the classroom". A receptive capacity is developed earlier than productive capacity.

CONCLUSION

It means that much of the communicative data understood by the learners will reappear in their talk in the early stage. They can produce speech at the minimal-communicative level. Learners move gradually through stages of inter-language development which contain errors, toward native speaker norms. The learner's mental processes concentrate first and foremost on finding meaning. It is therefore the semantic content of the words and basic word order that will be internalized first and it is these features that will appear in production first. The more redundant grammatical features will be attended to and internalized only when sufficient mental capacity is available to permit this.

REFERENCES

1. The Council of Europe. - Strasbourg, 1996. The final draft was published in 2001.
2. Using the CEFR : Principles of Good Practice. - CUP, 2011. -P.8
3. Current Perceptions and Practice and their Implications Ed. W.A. Renandya. - Singapore; SEAMEO Regional Language Centre, 2003. -P. 13